

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**SAFETY AND EFFICACY OF 10% SULPHUR OINTMENT FOR
THE TREATMENT OF SCABIES**Dr Bakhtawar Shaukat¹, Dr Sidra Aziz¹, Dr Saira Sarfraz²¹Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad,²Aziz Fatima Medical and Dental College, Faisalabad.

Article Received: May 2019

Accepted: June 2019

Published: July 2019

Abstract:**Objective:** To determine the safety and efficacy of 10% sulphur ointment in scabies.**Study Design:** An open label clinical trial.**Place and Duration:** This study is conducted in the Dermatology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for Six months duration from October 2018 to March 2019.**Methodology:** In this study sample, there were 65 patients with clinically diagnosed scabies, three were excluded from the follow-up and with 10% sulphur ointment were treated. By questionnaire; Clinical data was recorded. Into 3 age groups; Patients were divided and sulphur ointment applications were given. Follow-up was performed on day 3, day 15, 1 month, 3 months and 6 months.**Results:** The efficacy and safety of sulphur ointment in scabies was found to be very important clinically to improve patient symptoms.**Conclusion:** Patients with scabies should recommend 10% sulphur ointment with a conventional therapy that significantly improves symptoms after adequate local administration.**Key Words:** discharge, 10% sulphur ointment, efficacy and safety.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Bakhtawar Shaukat,**

Faisalabad Medical University, Faisalabad.

QR code

Please cite this article in press Bakhtawar Shaukat et al., **Safety And Efficacy Of 10% Sulphur Ointment For The Treatment Of Scabies.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06[07].

INTRODUCTION:

Scabies is an important public health issue in many tropical and subtropical areas. Worldwide prevalence is estimated to be about 300 million per year and is more communal in older children, young adults, mothers of young children, and the elderly¹⁻³. An arthrope of order Acarina; It is caused scabies by the sarcoptes mite variety hominis, One symptom of scabies invasion is intense itching and redness that often worsen at night⁴⁻⁵. The lesion starts with small erythematous papules. The scabies diagnostic symptoms are burrows⁶. Sulphur has antibacterial, keratolytic and antifungal activity. In the past, it has been used for general dermatological diseases such as rosacea, acne vulgaris, dandruff, seborrheic dermatitis, warts and scabies⁷. Keratolytic effects should be mediated by the reaction between sulphur and cysteine in keratinocytes; wherein the antimicrobial effect is due to the conversion of sulphur into the perapantionic acid with normal flora of the skin or keratinocytes. Keratolytics dissolve intracellular substances in the stratum corneum of the skin. The epidermal cells swell, soften and then exfoliate.⁸ These drugs are used in hyperkeratotic lesions. The sulphur preparation for topical application has a low degree of toxicity. Sulphur is smelly and the sheets are stains⁹. The dosage is administered to the entire body in the bath for 3 consecutive nights and 24 hours after each administration. Sulphur is shown in infants, children and pregnancy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This open label clinical trial was held in the Dermatology Department of Mayo Hospital, Lahore for Six months duration from October 2018 to March 2019. The subjects participate in the study were evaluated by the Consultant Dermatologist. The patient's written consent was taken and detailed questionnaire was completed and their relatives was informed. Patients wishing to contribute in the analysis were evaluated by put on exclusion and inclusion criteria. According to age; into 3 groups, Patients were divided. Inclusion criteria are night pruritus, diagnosis of scabies in both sexes, the presence or absence of a lesion in the classical regions above 5 years of age and under 70 years of age, and a family history of similar diseases. 3 or more of the above criteria prepared the patient qualified to be included in the analysis. Exclusion criteria; breastfeeding women, pregnant women, patients treated last month, crusted scabies, patients with liver failure and diabetics or cardiovascular, neurological diseases and dermatological disorders. Appropriate patients were allocated to apply 10% sulphur ointment and sequential baths for 3 nights, 24 hours after each

administration, and repeated administration 15 days later. The study duration was three months with 5 follow-up visits. 65 total scabies patients were divided into three groups according to their age. By the appearance of new skin; clinical efficacy was assessed and pruritus assessed by visual analogue scales has both static and dynamic components. The dynamic component was rated on a scale of 0-6. Data were analyzed using SPSS 19.0.

RESULTS:

In the sulphur ointment group, the global average of visual analogue scale for pruritus on day 0 was 6.0 ± 0.00 , the mean VAS on day 3 was reduced to $\pm 3.63 \pm 0.06$ on day 3, the mean VAS was also reduced to 2.52 ± 0.08 on day 30 1.18 ± 0.17 , the mean VAS on day 60 was reduced to 0.92 ± 0.24 , and on the 90th day the mean VAS was increased to 1.26 ± 0.30 . This increase can be due to relapse in scabies patients, compared with 0 to 90 days, the average VAS was quite significant. Compared to the 90th day at day 0, the results were quite significant according to age groups, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Visual analog score (vas) in scabies treated patients on day-0 to day-90 sulfur ointment group

	Sulfur Ointment Group (n=65) Mean±SEM
Visual analog score (VAS)	
Day - 0	6.00 ± 0.00
Day - 3	3.63 ± 0.06
Day - 15	2.52 ± 0.08
Day - 30	1.18 ± 0.17
Day - 60	0.92 ± 0.24
Day - 90	1.26 ± 0.30**
Visual analog score (VAS) according to age groups (5-25 years)	
Day - 0	6.00 ± 0.00
Day - 3	3.41 ± 0.11
Day - 15	2.41 ± 0.14
Day - 30	0.95 ± 0.29
Day - 60	0.91 ± 0.43
Day - 90	1.36 ± 0.55**
26-45 years	
Day - 0	6.00 ± 0.00
Day - 3	3.60 ± 0.11
Day - 15	2.50 ± 0.14
Day - 30	1.30 ± 0.30
Day - 60	0.90 ± 0.41
Day - 90	1.25 ± 0.49**
46-70 years	
Day - 0	6.00 ± 0.00
Day - 3	3.90 ± 0.07
Day - 15	2.65 ± 0.17
Day - 30	1.30 ± 0.30
Day - 60	0.95 ± 0.44
Day - 90	1.15 ± 0.53**

**=Highly significant.

The total number of patients with scabies developed new lesions, especially on the 15th day and in 8.1% (5), 14.5% on the 30th day in (9), and 17.7% on the 60th day of scabies in (11), on the 90th day, the percentage increased to 22.6% in scabies (14), which may be due to relapse in scabies. The appearance of

the new lesions was not significant. The recovery rate of 62 (95.4%) patients with scabies on day 30 was 88.7% (55), 80.6% on day 60 (50), and the percentage of patients treated on day 90 was reduced to 79% (49). This decrease may be due to repeat and resistance compared to day 90 at day 0, the cure rate was quite pronounced. When we compare 0 days to 90 days, the cure rate was quite significant according to age groups. The safety profile was evaluated clinically with complaints of adverse effects in patients treated during the study period of drug administration, with no major adverse effects other than burning. The light burning percentage was 3.2%. (Table II).

Table 2: Appearance of new lesion in scabies treated patients sulfur ointment group

Follow-up available	Sulfur Ointment Group (n=65)
Appearance of new lesion (P value 0.158)	
Day - 3	-
Day - 15	5 (8.1%)
Day - 30	9 (14.5%)
Day - 60	11 (17.7%)
Day - 90	15 (24.2%)
Appearance of new lesion according to age groups 5-25 years (n=22)	
Day - 15	2 (3.2%)
Day - 30	4 (6.4%)
Day - 60	4 (6.4%)
Day - 90	5 (8.1%)
26-45 years (n=20) (p value 0.868)	
Day - 3	-
Day - 15	3 (4.8%)
Day - 30	3 (4.8%)
Day - 60	5 (8.1%)
Day - 90	5 (8.1%)
46-70 years (n=20) (P value 1.000)	
Day - 3	-
Day - 15	-
Day - 30	2 (3.2%)
Day - 60	2 (3.2%)
Day - 90	5 (8.1%)

DISCUSSION

Scabies are widespread in our society and the instincts and implants of traditional scabies are difficult to implant. This often results in higher failure rates due to mismatch or re-seeding. Reported incidence of scabies in Karachi has 22.7% more than other infections and shows a worrying prevalence indicating a lack of awareness of this common skin problem¹⁰. Absolute confirmation can be made by discovery of certainties and microscopic examination¹¹. Scabies treatment is as important as making an accurate diagnosis. The patient should receive adequate instructions on the use of scabicide. The cure rate of the patients was 76.6%, and only two patients showed

a slight burning in this study; it used sulphur ointment and found a cure rate of 71% recommended to be a safe and inexpensive option¹². In this study, the rate of recovery was assessed by the presence of a new skin formation. Participants without new lesions were considered to be treated¹³. All participants were asked about itching reduction in the EVA as 0/25/50/75/100/100. On day 0, pruritus was considered to be 100% and our results coincided with other studies reporting that sulphur was acting against emergence. In another study in Pakistan, they said that sulphur is the oldest anti-spastic used and is available in very effective, inexpensive and safe preparations. In this study, these participants who showed new lesions and complained of itching developing resistance and relapse due to poor compliance. Sulphur can be used in infants, children and pregnancy¹⁴. Inadequate administration of drugs is the main factor of pharmacological resistance in the study. Repeated scabicide prescriptions have been proposed to reduce the pharmacological resistance of scabies. This highly contagious nature of the disease requires that all other household members be treated at the same time if they do not have symptoms¹⁵. To ensure good control, you have to improve hygiene and mass treatment campaigns, integrate awareness and education.

CONCLUSION

10% sulphur ointment is safe and effective, but is recommended with conventional treatment.

REFERENCES:

1. Sanders, Kristen M., Leigh A. Nattkemper, Jordan D. Rosen, Hjalte H. Andersen, Jeremy Hsiang, Paolo Romanelli, Charlotte Bernigaud, Jacques Guillot, Olivier Chosidow, and Gil Yosipovitch. "Non-Histaminergic Itch Mediators Elevated in the Skin of a Porcine Model of Scabies and of Human Scabies Patients." *Journal of Investigative Dermatology* 139, no. 4 (2019): 971-973.
2. Sunderkötter, C., Aebischer, A., Neufeld, M., Löser, C., Kreuter, A., Bialek, R., Hamm, H. and Feldmeier, H., 2019. Increase of scabies in Germany and development of resistant mites? Evidence and consequences. *JDDG: Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft*, 17(1), pp.15-23.
3. Romani, Lucia, Michael Marks, Oliver Sokana, Titus Nasi, Bakaai Kamoriki, Billie Cordell, Handan Wand et al. "Efficacy of mass drug administration with ivermectin for control of scabies and impetigo, with coadministration of azithromycin: a single-arm community intervention trial." *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 19, no. 5 (2019): 510-518.

4. May, Philippa J., Steven YC Tong, Andrew C. Steer, Bart J. Currie, Ross M. Andrews, Jonathan R. Carapetis, and Asha C. Bowen. "Treatment, prevention and public health management of impetigo, scabies, crusted scabies and fungal skin infections in endemic populations: a systematic review." *Tropical Medicine & International Health* 24, no. 3 (2019): 280-293.
5. van der Linden, Naomi, Kees van Gool, Karen Gardner, Helen Dickinson, Jason Agostino, David G. Regan, Michelle Dowden, and Rosalie Viney.
6. Chosidow, Olivier, and Roderick J. Hay. "Control of scabies and secondary impetigo: optimising treatment effectiveness in endemic settings." *The Lancet Infectious Diseases* 19, no. 5 (2019): 454-456.
7. Barker, Caitlin M. Adams, M. James Alexander, and Antonia L. Altomare. "Establishing a mass prophylaxis clinic during a hospital scabies outbreak." *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology* 40, no. 2 (2019): 261-263.
8. Pisano, Simone RR, Marie-Pierre Rysler-Degiorgis, Luca Rossi, Andrea Peano, Karin Keckeis, and Petra Roosje. "Sarcoptic Mange of Fox Origin in Multiple Farm Animals and Scabies in Humans, Switzerland, 2018." *Emerging infectious diseases* 25, no. 6 (2019): 1235.
9. Pisano, Simone RR, Marie-Pierre Rysler-Degiorgis, Luca Rossi, Andrea Peano, Karin Keckeis, and Petra Roosje. "Sarcoptic Mange of Fox Origin in Multiple Farm Animals and Scabies in Humans, Switzerland, 2018." *Emerging infectious diseases* 25, no. 6 (2019): 1235.
10. Hashimoto, T., T. Satoh, and H. Yokozeki. "Pruritus in ordinary scabies: IL-31 from macrophages induced by overexpression of thymic stromal lymphopoietin and periostin." *Allergy* (2019).
11. Aussy A, Houivet E, Hébert V, Colas-Cailleux H, Laaengh N, Richard C, Ouvry M, Boulard C, Léger S, Litrowski N, Benichou J.
12. Tripathi, Raghav, Konrad D. Knusel, Harib H. Ezaldein, Jeremy S. Bordeaux, and Jeffrey F. Scott. "Emergency Department Visits due to Scabies in the United States
13. Vijayan, Vini, Elizabeth Marrero, Anna Gaspar, Christy Wisdom, Michele D. Honeycutt, and W. Matthew Linam. "Outbreak of scabies in a neonatal intensive care unit." *Infection Control & Hospital Epidemiology* (2019): 1-2.
14. Rihatmadja, R., Miranda, E., Wicaksono, M.M. and Widaty, S., 2019. Why are they hard to treat? A preliminary survey to predict important factors causing persistent scabies among students of religion-affiliated boarding schools in Indonesia. *Dermatology Reports*.
15. Hoffmann, Johanna Charlotte, Rotraut Mößner, Michael Peter Schön, and Undine Lippert. "Topical scabies therapy with permethrin is effective and well tolerated in infants younger than two months." *JDDG: Journal der Deutschen Dermatologischen Gesellschaft* (2019).